

Water requirement for peanut following rice in Bangalore

K. Joseph and G. V. Havanagi, Agronomy Department, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, India

We studied the water requirement for peanut in summer rice fallows 1983 and 1984. One irrigation was given all treatments at planting. Treatments were irrigation at 40% soil moisture deficit at 30-cm soil depth, at flowering, pod formation, and pod filling; and at pod formation. The water table receded from 20.6 to 63.3 cm during the crop period.

Water use, yield, and yield attributes of peanut following rice under different irrigation levels.

Character	Irrigation level ^a			LSD (0.05)
	T1	T2	T3	
Plant height at maturity (cm)	40.5	41.5	38.7	ns
Dry matter production at harvest (g/plant)	9.3	10.2	9.9	ns
Test weight (g/100 kernels)	28.9	28.7	28.9	ns
Shelling percentage	74.2	73.4	73.7	ns
Pod yield (t/ha)	2.2	2.2	2.1	ns
Water use efficiency	77.8	112.7	179.9	7.0
Water use (cm)	28.8	17.2	8.9	-

^aT1= at 40% soil moisture deficit; T2 = at flowering, pod formation, pod filling; T3 = at pod formation.

Growth and yield attributes were statistically similar (see table). Water use efficiency was significantly higher with additional irrigation (8.86 cm) only at pod formation. ■

Rice variety to fit cropping patterns in Tripura, India

S. K. Gupta and S. Laskar, ICAR Research Complex for N. E. H. Region, Tripura Centre, Lembucherra 799210, India

Rice variety Mahsuri is popular in Tripura but its 150-d duration delays sowing of succeeding crops potato, wheat, or mustard and preceding crops jute and rice.

We compared four 125-d duration rice varieties with Mahsuri during 1982 and 1983 wet seasons and 1983 and 1984 dry seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Soil was loamy with pH 5.5, 0.06% total N, 0.94% organic C, and CEC 9.97

Yield of rice cultivars to fit different cropping patterns In Tripura, India, 1982-84.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)							
	Wet season				Dry season			
	1982	1983	Mean	Productivity (kg/d)	1983	1984	Mean	Productivity (kg/d)
Mahsuri	2.6	2.3	2.4	16.3	2.5	2.7	2.6	16.5
Jaya	1.9	2.2	2.1	16.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	21.7
Vijaya	2.6	2.6	2.6	20.6	3.8	3.1	3.4	26.1
CR75-93 (Saber)	2.6	2.6	2.6	20.6	3.9	4.5	4.2	31.2
IR36	2.2	2.5	2.4	19.6	3.7	3.4	3.5	27.6
LSD ^a (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	-	0.8	0.9	0.8	-

^ans - not significant

meq/100 g soil. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing; fertilizer was 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Grain yields in the dry season differed significantly. Highest yield was with Saber (see table).

Yields in the wet season did not differ significantly. ■

Relay cropping in upland rice fallows

T. Barik and K. C. Sahoo, Regional Research Station, Bhawanipatna, Kalahandi, Orissa 766001, India

We evaluated the effect of rice varieties Jajati and Assamchudi at three densities with six pulses as relay crops 1985-86 to 1987-88. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications.

Soil was medium black, clayey, with medium fertility and pH 7.8.

Jajati rice yielded 0.2 t/ha more than local variety Assamchudi. Rice variety

and density had no significant effect on relay crop yield.

Highest pulse yield was with lathyrus, and lowest was with black gram (see table). Local field gram yielded higher than improved field pea. Black gram had

unusually lanky growth and poor stand, which could be due to low temperatures.

Highest net profit was with bengal gram, followed by lathyrus. improved pea, and local field pea. ■

Yield and return from pulses grown as relay crops following rice. Orissa, India, 1985-86 to 1987-88.

Crop	Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Cost of cultivation (\$)	Net profit/ha (\$)	Duration (d)
Bengal gram	OG 62	0.21	32.85	59.12	109
Lathyrus	Local	0.22	21.90	41.75	104
Black gram	T9	0.03	16.42	(-)7.23	92
Lentil	T397	0.10	21.90	13.87	107
Improved field pea	Rachna	0.15	32.85	31.97	102
Local field pea	Local	0.19	27.37	27.52	101